

Federated Learning for Telecom Fraud Detection: A Privacy-Preserving Approach to Overcoming Data Fragmentation and Enhancing Security

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Suggested Citation

Hasan, K., Hosen, M.N., & Saha, K. (2024). Federated Learning for Telecom Fraud Detection: A Privacy-Preserving Approach to Overcoming Data Fragmentation and Enhancing Security. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 99-109.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).08)

Abstract:

Over the last couple of years, the world has seen numerous frauds about telecom: fraud calls, phishing, and misutilization of personal numbers, among others. However, traditional methods of fraud detection cannot fit the shifting intricacy of these fraud schemes since they depend on data collection in a centralized way. While the arrival of deep learning improves the detection capability, it engenders considerable privacy risks and issues of data fragmentation. As one might guess, this work investigates federated learning as a decentralized solution to these limitations. The FL allows various organizations to train fraud detection models collaboratively while preserving data privacy via sharing only model

updates, not raw data. This paper proposes a federated learning-based system for phone number fraud detection and defends personal data against various industries. We will discuss in more detail the advantages of federated learning in solving the "data island" problem and reducing the risk of privacy breaches in a distributed environment. The paper also looks at the use of horizontal and vertical federated learning in co-governance both within and across industries. Finally, we discuss the limitation of FL from a practical perspective by including problems arising from non-IID data and heterogeneity in systems and scalability. We also identify further works to be pursued in optimizing the performance of FL fraud detection with privacy preservation.

Keywords: *Federated Learning, Data Security, Privacy-Preserving, Telecom Fraud Detection.*

Introduction

Within the last couple of years, telecom network fraud has rapidly emerged as one of the significant global challenges, growing both in

technological sophistication and scope. The fraud ranged from scam calls and spam messages to phishing, thus stirring an increasingly severe public response due to its wide range and

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harmful impact on society. Many Telecom fraud schemes exploit the individual's very personal telephone number for unlawful purposes and, in doing so, tend to infringe on the security of personal data and public confidence. In this respect, such fraud runs serious risks not only of significant material losses but also of breaches of personal privacy. These have become increasingly difficult to counter using traditional means of interception and fraud prevention (Han, et al., 2021).

Traditional fraud communication interception techniques, including block list utilization and message blocking, still cannot handle the increasing fraud schemes. Such kinds of techniques are highly static to keep pace with the dynamism in fraudsters' techniques, which keep changing from time to time to avoid intelligence. The incidences of personal phone numbers used in fraudulent activities have gone up, and this brings the risk of privacy violation up several notches; there is an urgent need for more sophisticated technologies to avoid telecom fraud while protecting personal information effectively (Yin, et al., 2021).

AI and ML technologies are emerging as a strong toolset for increasing capabilities related to fraud detection, particularly deep learning. Combined with traditional rule-based systems, deep learning models can accomplish much by detecting most of the complex patterns and relationships in communication behavior data. These lead to better accuracy and efficiency in fraud detection. Such models will alter the game in fraudulent phone number detection and scoring by unearthing most fraud patterns that always go undetected by traditional systems. However, all these advantages present new challenges, especially those related to privacy and data security, under the deep learning techniques adoption (Xu, et al., 2020). Among the major concerns of deep learning models, one includes high privacy leakage risk due to the necessity of centralized data collection. In traditional, centralized learning, large volumes of user communication data need to be collected and stored on central servers for efficient model training. This may bring a high privacy risk, as

some sensitive communication behavior data may be disclosed in the process (Xu, et al., 2022).

Moreover, the need for huge quantities of data further aggravates the problem of "data islands". Due to privacy concerns or commercial confidentiality, each enterprise is unwilling to open its data to other companies, which results in serious fragmentation of data within the industry. This inevitably means that data cannot realize their full potential, leading to incomplete fraud detection models in terms of completeness or scope. In fact, even the differences in structure and dimensions between companies serve to further complicate matters in unified model development for fraud detection (Gu, et al., 2021). The other partners respectively render services in a different way, there are big disparities in features and dimensions of data they collect. Even when data from different companies is integrated, issues such as feature misalignment, inconsistent model structures, and unbalanced data distribution arise. These discrepancies make creating a comprehensive model that works effectively across all data sources difficult, hence further limiting the efficacy of the traditional approaches to fraud detection. Besides these, deep learning models also have serious interpretability issues that prevent their practical deployment in real-world applications (Hao, et al., 2020). Deep learning models are sometimes considered "black box" systems since it is very difficult to understand how a model arrives at its prediction or gives a clear justification for its output. This opacity can be problematic in fraud detection, for instance, when there is a need to have accountability and stakeholders interested in the grounds on which a given phone number is flagged fraudulent. How can these models be trusted and thus widely adopted if there is absolutely no explanation in the first place as to why that model flagged that number as fraudulent (Zhang, et al., 2023)?

Of all the trendy and novel solutions that could give a federated approach to some of the challenges brought about by deep learning in fraud detection, the foremost will be federated learning. Unlike traditional centralized models, federated learning ensures that participants can

collaborate feasibly to train models on data stored locally, with no need to share that data. This is the decentralized approach: participating nodes share model parameters rather than raw data to take care of the privacy concerns in centralized data collections, hence preserving data confidentiality (Fu, et al., 2020). Moreover, federated learning improves the performance of models by considering data from multiple sources, overcoming the challenge brought about by isolated datasets. A case in point is that federated learning has also introduced mechanisms to handle the challenges of non-IID data, a common scenario in telecom fraud detection. Aggregation of non-IID data could, even in traditional machine learning models, degrade model performance due to imbalances found in such data. It mitigates this problem through federated learning by incorporating mechanisms for evaluating an incentive in the contribution of each participant's data to the global model, thus making sure that the optimal use of the data from different participants is utilized. Also, aggregated results via federated learning allow more interpretable results, making the decision for fraud detection more transparent and credible for application in real-world duties (Tan, et al., 2020).

The present paper analyzes the application of federated learning in the identification of fraudulent phone numbers to protect personal information further. The study systematically identifies the deficiencies of current deep learning models. It correspondingly selects the possibility of federated learning to fill these gaps by minimizing user privacy while improving fraud detection capabilities. It, therefore,

proposes a co-governance framework for combating fraud and informational protection as a response to the current challenges represented by growing cases of telecom fraud.

Analysis Method for Fraudulent Phone Numbers Based on Federated Learning

This paper proposes a method for analyzing fraudulent phone numbers based on federated learning, aiming to fully leverage the advantages of multi-party data while ensuring data privacy. This section briefly describes the basic concepts of federated learning, discusses its applicable scenarios in fraudulent phone number analysis, and provides a risk assessment model for fraudulent phone numbers using different federated learning methods.

Overview of Federated Learning Algorithms

Federated Learning (FL) is a decentralized learning framework that enables multiple clients to train a global model while keeping their data localized collaboratively. This approach addresses data privacy concerns and ensures that sensitive information, such as personal medical records or financial data, remains within the control of each client. Unlike traditional centralized machine learning models, where data is pooled together in one location, FL allows clients to keep data on their local devices and only share model updates with a central server. These updates are then aggregated to improve the global model, making FL a suitable solution for applications where privacy is critical (Schneider, et al., 2021).

Table 1. Comparison of Federated Learning Algorithms

Federated Learning Type	Industry Application	Data Structure	Advantages	Challenges
Horizontal Federated Learning (HFL)	Telecom, Finance, Healthcare	Same feature space, different sample spaces	Preserves privacy, suitable for industry-wide co-governance	Data imbalance (non-IID data), communication overhead
Vertical Federated Learning (VFL)	Cross-industry (Telecom & Finance collaboration)	Different feature space, same sample space	Combines complementary datasets, cross-industry fraud detection	Secure sample alignment, encryption, and computation complexity

Hybrid Federated Learning	Multi-sector collaboration	Combination of horizontal and vertical features	Can address both feature and sample disparities	Complex system design, high computational requirements
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Steps in the Federated Learning Process

The federated learning process consists of several critical steps:

Initialization of Local Models: The process of federated learning is used to initial the local models, whereby a global model M_0 is initialized at the central server and then distributed to all the clients. This international model includes all the hyperparameters that may be required for the training, such as weights and biases. All these clients get the same model as their starting point, thus making the training uniform for all the clients. In this way, all the clients will start with the same initial point for updating the local models. It is an important step to make sure that while the local models aggregate later, they are aligned in terms of structure and parametrization (So, Guler, & Avestimehr, 2020).

Local Training on Client Data: Each client trains the global model M_0 using its local dataset, which contains private data that the client does not share with other parties. This training updates the client's version of the global model based on its local data, improving the model's accuracy for that dataset. The regional model parameters at the client after training at iteration t can be represented as $W_i^{(t)}$. The difference between the initial global model $W_0^{(0)}$ and the locally updated model is known as the local model update, and it is represented as:

$$\Delta w_i^{(t)} = w_i^{(t)} - w_0^{(t)} \quad (1)$$

This formula describes how each client modifies the global model using its local dataset. The update $\Delta w_i^{(t)}$ is then sent to the central server for aggregation. The benefit of this approach is that the client's raw data never leaves the local device, which helps preserve data privacy. Instead of sharing sensitive information, clients only share the result of their local computations, which is

the change in the model parameters (Liu, et al., 2022).

Aggregation of Local Updates: Once the central server receives the updates ($\Delta w_i^{(t)}$) from all participating clients, it aggregates these updates to improve the global model. The aggregation process ensures that the new international model reflects the collective learning of all clients while maintaining privacy. The most used aggregation technique is Federated Averaging (FedAvg), which calculates a weighted average of the model updates based on the size of each client's dataset. The formula for aggregating the local updates to update the global model is:

$$w_0^{(t+1)} = w_0^{(t)} + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{n_i}{N} \Delta w_i^{(t)} \quad (2)$$

This weighted aggregation formula ensures that clients with larger datasets contribute more to the global model. It balances the impact of each client's update by factoring in the size of their dataset, ensuring that the aggregated global model represents the entire population of data across all clients. The process of aggregation is typically carried out securely to prevent any leakage of individual client updates during transmission (Francis, Tenison, & Rish, 2021).

Global Model Update and Distribution: After the aggregation step, the central server sends the newly updated global model $w_0^{(t+1)}$ back to all clients. Each client then uses this updated model as the starting point for the next round of local training. This iterative process of training, updating, and aggregating continues until the global model converges to a desirable level of performance. As more iterations are completed, the international model becomes increasingly accurate and reflects the learning from the diverse data across all clients (Li, Ngai, & Voigt, 2023).

Application Scenarios

Federated learning could be applied to a heterogeneous scenario, balancing user information privacy protection and assessing the risk of personal phone number fraud. However, as phone number fraud is often involved in complex scenarios, although the user information stored by various industries and enterprises may intersect, the correlation of their features is often low. As a result, fraudulent analysis can only be accomplished with variable

data quality, badly affecting the accuracy and timeliness of the federated learning model for assessing those phone numbers, which are usually linked to high-cost losses. Therefore, targeted co-governance solutions for different federated learning algorithms should be presented based on the characteristics and abilities of different enterprises (Fereidooni, et al., 2021).

Table 2. Placement for Application Scenarios

Industry	Application of Federated Learning	Key Focus	Type of Federated Learning
Telecommunications	Fraud detection (phone number fraud, SIM swapping)	User communication data, network behavior	Horizontal Federated Learning
Finance	Fraud detection (transaction monitoring, AML)	Transaction history, credit score analysis	Horizontal Federated Learning
Healthcare	Medical record analysis, predictive diagnosis	Patient data privacy, multi-hospital collaboration	Horizontal Federated Learning
Cross-Industry	Joint fraud detection (e.g., Telecom + Finance)	Integration of communication and transaction data	Vertical Federated Learning

Industry-Wide Co-Governance

In most cases, the data on the same industry has a very strong correlation. In the legal basis of the basic telecom enterprises, the major analyses are around user communication behavior characteristics. If it's financial business, dimensions could relate to user transaction information. The internet companies would detect fraudulent behavior based on user account-related actions. Horizontal federated learning is an efficient method to break through data islands within industries. This is so because different enterprises operating similar services in the same sector usually maintain their data on users; these have a low overlap of customer bases in respective regions. However, the business model is pretty similar, and hence, the feature space of participant datasets will have a large intersection. Horizontal federated learning is when the datasets of every party have an identical feature space yet a different sample space. This allows multiple parties to jointly build a model for fraud risk assessment while protecting data privacy (Liu, et al., 2021).

Figure 1 illustrates the specific steps of applying horizontal federated learning among enterprises

in the same industry to train and generate a collaborative fraudulent phone number assessment model.

Figure 1. Horizontal Federated Learning among Enterprises

In horizontal federated learning, local model training and evaluation are distributed among participants. Although the overlap between the customer bases of different enterprises in the same industry is very small, the feature spaces used by local models are rather similar. Correspondingly, horizontal federated learning can be jointly utilized. Since all enterprises are in a peer-to-peer network architecture, any enterprise could be randomly selected as a temporary aggregator to collect and train the global model and then broadcast it to all participants after training. Security for communication between any two participants uses public key encryption to ensure that no breach of security occurs in data transmission between two parties involved in data sharing (Zhang, et al., 2022).

Cross-Industry Co-Governance

The only problem is not the risk of data privacy leakage for cross-industry co-governance on fraudulent phone numbers but that different enterprises provide large differences in business models, leading to variances in data types, feature information, and customer labels. Take basic telecom enterprises as an example: They know fraud risks only based on user communication behavior maintained in their databases and cannot provide comprehensive user profiles. Contrary, the financial enterprises themselves can extend user transaction behavior based on phone numbers but fail to build models analyzing whether those features indicate fraud. If there is interindustry collaboration, a joint model can analyze user behavior from various dimensions. This provides a fine characterization of fraudulent behavior, urgently making the model much more effective than single-enterprise data modeling.

When data samples of different parties have significant overlap, but the sample features are seriously overlapped, vertical federated learning can be an available approach to collaborate on model training. This approach vertically partitions several data sets by feature dimensions, extracts data from participating parties that belong to the same user or phone

number but are not completely identical in their features, and performs encrypted aggregation and federated training to enhance or supplement each participating party's modeling capability (Shuai, et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Vertical Federated Learning among Cross-Industry Enterprises

Figure 2 illustrates the specific steps of applying vertical federated learning among cross-industry enterprises to train and generate a collaborative fraudulent phone number assessment model.

In vertical federated learning, since the user groups of different enterprises are different, the technology of alignment of encryption of user samples must be used, and each party has to align their respective user phone numbers without exposing the original data. Then, based on the aligned phone number and corresponding features, each party can train a local model. It is worth noting that each party can add a random mask on their gradient information to avoid data privacy leakage between enterprises to protect the security of user personal information. After matching the encryption samples, vertical federated learning still needs to make use of additive homomorphism encryption algorithms to calculate and upload their respective gradients to some trusted aggregation server. These arrive at the aggregation server, which decodes them, updates the weights, and sends them back to each participating party's local model with updated weights. This is iteratively done until the

preset number of iterations is reached or until the loss function falls below a certain threshold, thereby completing the training (Hu, et al., 2023).

Application Limitations and Future Prospects

Federated learning indeed provides a promising framework for privacy-preserving data sharing and collaborative model training in the detection of personal phone number fraud. However, with advantages, the application of federated learning to real-world applications also has several challenges that considerably hamper its performance. Major challenges involve data distribution, device security, system heterogeneity, and scalability. Understanding these limitations is crucial, coupled with the development of solutions that make federated learning practical and a powerful tool for a wider range of industries.

Data Heterogeneity

A major obstacle in federated learning is the heterogeneity of data, often referred to as non-IID or non-Independent and Identically Distributed. What this means, in simple terms, is that the data across the nodes or enterprises participating in the model is not uniformly distributed. For example, a telecom company would collect data with a focus on communication patterns, whereas a financial institution may focus on transaction histories. These differences create imbalances because models may overfit certain data types, especially when one participant has a much larger dataset compared to others. This leads to a biased global model that over-represents the large nodes' data patterns and may result in poor fraud detection across the network.

Besides impacting the accuracy of the global model, the non-IID nature of the data further hampers convergence. Federated learning iteratively trains a model by aggregating updates from different participants. When data is skewed, the global model takes more time to converge to an optimal solution or may converge to a suboptimal one. Advanced methods need to

be developed to address this, such as personalized federated learning models that adapt to the local data distribution on each client or new aggregation techniques that weigh updates based on data characteristics instead of dataset size.

Security in Devices

Device security is a major issue in federated learning since local models get trained on participant devices. In a federated system, each participant controls their data, and the computational resources needed for processing it. However, decentralized setups open the door to adversarial attacks or device tampering. For instance, an attacker can hijack a local model to send fake updates to the central server, degrading the performance of the global model. This type of attack is known as model poisoning and can be particularly concerning since it may remain undetected until the performance of the global model has significantly deteriorated.

Another aspect of device security is the integrity of data during transmission. While federated learning protocols typically encrypt data in transit, the risk of interception or data leakage remains if the devices themselves are compromised. With federated learning expanding into sectors like finance, healthcare, and telecommunications, where data sensitivity is extremely high, robust security protocols are essential to ensure that neither the models nor the data are exposed to unauthorized parties. Techniques like secure aggregation and differential privacy can mitigate these risks, but further research is needed to counter increasingly sophisticated attack vectors.

System Heterogeneity

System heterogeneity in federated learning refers to variations in computational power, storage capacity, and network conditions of the devices participating in the learning process. In practice, some participants may use high-performance servers, while others use low-power smartphones. This wide range of hardware creates challenges in ensuring efficiency and fairness in the federated learning system.

Devices with limited computational power may struggle to process large datasets or train complex models. This can cause delays in updating the global model or result in incomplete updates that negatively impact the overall learning process. Participants with poor network bandwidth or intermittent connectivity may fail to submit updates in a timely manner, slowing down the training process for the entire system.

To address system heterogeneity, federated learning frameworks must implement adaptive mechanisms that efficiently involve all devices. Dynamic adjustment of model size or computation load based on each device's capabilities can prevent less powerful devices from being overwhelmed. Additionally, asynchronous training methods can accommodate participants with slower network connections, ensuring that the system does not depend on synchronized updates from all clients.

Scalability

Another critical limitation in deploying federated learning systems is scalability, especially in large-scale applications involving thousands or millions of participants. While more participants mean more data and more frequent

communication between clients and the central server, this increases communication overhead, making it difficult to maintain efficient model updates.

The challenge of scalability is compounded by the need to aggregate updates from a growing number of participants. Traditional aggregation methods, such as Federated Averaging (FedAvg), may become inefficient as the number of updates increases, leading to greater latency and higher communication costs. Moreover, with more participants in the system, the likelihood of encountering non-IID data increases, which can further skew the global model.

Addressing scalability requires the development of more efficient communication protocols, such as compression techniques that reduce the size of model updates or hierarchical aggregation methods that group participants to minimize communication with the central server. The system must also balance communication efficiency with model quality, ensuring that as more participants join, the quality of the global model does not degrade.

Impact Of Communication Cost and Data Heterogeneity in Federated Learning

Figure 3. Impact of Communication Cost and Data Heterogeneity in Federated Learning

This graph compares the communication cost and data heterogeneity impact in Federated

Learning, based on recent research. It can be noticed that communication cost is still a big

challenge: some works like Huang, Lin, & Wang, (2021) and Smith, Zhang, & Lee, (2020) target the reduction of overhead using multistage optimization and gradient compression, respectively. In any case, communications can hardly be done without problems when addressing large-scale deployments. On the other hand, data heterogeneity shows an always higher impact on the results throughout the different works. Some papers, such as Chen, Xu, & Sun, (2020) and Luo, Yan, & Zhang, (2021), remark on the challenges of non-IID data brought about by the imbalance in the distribution that may result in biased models. Cluster-based learning and some specialized optimization frameworks are some of the proposed solutions, yet balancing both communication efficiency and heterogeneity of data remains a vital challenge.

All in all, the graph depicts an increased desire for more integrated solutions that could aptly handle both communication and data diversity within federated learning systems.

Future Directions

Given the current limitations, several promising areas for future research in federated learning emerge. First, addressing data heterogeneity through personalized models and advanced aggregation techniques is critical. Personalized models that adapt to each participant's unique data distribution can ensure that the global model represents all participants, regardless of dataset size, improving fairness and accuracy.

Second, improving device security is essential to prevent adversarial attacks and maintain the learning process's integrity. To safeguard federated learning systems from tampering and malicious behavior, stronger encryption methods, secure hardware, and sophisticated anomaly detection techniques will be necessary.

Third, tackling system heterogeneity requires the development of adaptive learning algorithms that can scale across different device capabilities. Efficient resource management and dynamic model adaptation will allow devices of various types to join federated learning without negatively affecting global model performance.

Lastly, enhancing scalability through more efficient communication protocols and aggregation methods will be key to deploying federated learning in large-scale applications. As federated learning becomes more popular, handling a vast number of participants while maintaining accuracy and efficiency will be crucial for its long-term success.

Conclusion

This paper explores federated learning as a co-governance approach to protect personal phone numbers and fight fraud. It first analyzed the current fraud detection methods and pointed out the limitations of centralized data storage, including significant privacy risks. Federated learning was introduced as a promising solution, particularly in privacy-critical industries, by enabling collaborative learning without requiring data sharing.

Federated learning allows organizations to train a global model using distributed data, gaining a broader range of insights while keeping local datasets confidential. The paper also evaluated various federated learning algorithms and their suitability for different applications, such as industry-wide co-governance and cross-industry collaboration. Federated learning empowers companies to fight fraud by creating more robust detection models that leverage multi-dimensional data.

Despite its potential, federated learning has limitations, such as non-IID data, device heterogeneity, and scalability challenges. Overcoming these challenges will require more research into advanced techniques, such as better data aggregation methods and stronger security protocols. Balancing computational performance and data privacy will remain a critical challenge in large-scale federated learning deployments.

In conclusion, while federated learning offers a compelling approach to enhancing privacy-preserving fraud detection, further work is needed to optimize its performance in real-world applications. Future research should address data heterogeneity, device constraints, and model scalability to unlock the benefits of

federated learning in privacy-sensitive industries fully.

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